

How to file a complaint

MOTHER EARTH MSCA POSTDOCTORAL FELLOWSHIP

BRUSSELS
SCHOOL OF
GOVERNANCE

HOUSE OF
SUSTAINABLE TRANSITIONS

Queen Mary
University of London

Funded by
the European Union

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How to complaint / Alice Lopes Fabris. — 1st ed. — Brussels: MSCA Mother Earth Project, 2025.

Booklet developed within the framework of the Project Mother Earth (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions), funded by the European Union.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18185005

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Lopes Fabris, A. (2025). *How to complaint* (1st ed.). VUB & MSCA Mother Earth Project.

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Introduction

This booklet serves as a practical guide for understanding the processes available to bring complaints about violations of cultural rights linked to environmental degradation before regional and international human rights and labour mechanisms. Navigating these systems can often be complex, involving specialised legal language and specific procedural requirements.

We present this guide to help you understand the available avenues when domestic solutions are exhausted. We provide an overview of the three key bodies that hear complaints from individuals and communities. Our aim is to demystify the process by outlining the specific procedures for:

- The Inter-American System (e.g., petitions before the Commission that can lead to cases before the IACtHR).
- UN Treaty Bodies and Special Procedures (e.g., individual communications and thematic mandates).
- The ILO Supervisory System (e.g., representations and complaints regarding ratified Conventions, particularly ILO Convention No. 169).

This section is designed to empower communities, advocates, and their legal counsel with a starting point for understanding how to seek accountability and redress for the harm caused by environmental degradation to their way of life.

Inter-American Court of Human Rights

(IACtHR)

Inter-American Human Rights System

If you live in the Americas and believe your human rights have been violated by a member state of the Organization of American States (OAS), you may be able to file a complaint with the Inter-American Human Rights System (IAHRS).

This system is made up of two main bodies:

1. The Inter-American Commission on Human Rights (IACHR or “the Commission”)
2. The Inter-American Court of Human Rights (“the Court”)

These bodies work together to ensure that OAS member states respect the human rights protections laid out in regional treaties like the American Convention on Human Rights (also known as the Pact of San José).

What is the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights?

The Commission was established in 1959 and is composed of seven independent human rights experts. It monitors, promotes, and protects human rights in the region.

What Can the Commission Do?

- Visit countries to observe human rights conditions.
- Issue thematic or country-specific reports.
- Urge States to take urgent protective actions (called precautionary measures).
- Receive individual petitions (complaints) from people or organisations alleging violations of human rights under Inter-American treaties.

The IACHR receives the petition, analyses it, tries to negotiate with the State, and if it understands that there was a violation, it can bring the complaint to the Court.

To file a petition

You can file a petition even if you are:

- A victim,
- Representing someone else,
- A group or organisation.

You can base your complaint on violations:

- The American Convention on Human Rights,
- The American Declaration of the Rights and Duties of Man, or
- Other Inter-American treaties (if the State has ratified them).

Who Can You File a Complaint Against?

You can file a complaint only against countries that are members of the OAS, not against people, companies, or other groups.

- By action: when government officials commit the violation.
- By acquiescence: when the government knew about the violation but allowed it to happen.
- By omission: when the government failed to stop or investigate the abuse.

The IACHR cannot prosecute or sentence individuals for crimes. It only determines whether a State violated international human rights obligations.

Before You File:

Before sending a complaint, you usually need to use all legal options in your country, including appealing to the highest court.

Exceptions: You can skip this step if:

- Your country's legal system is ineffective.
- You were denied access to justice.
- There were unreasonable delays in your case.
- You are facing extreme poverty or danger.

Once you have finished domestic legal steps, file your complaint within six months of the final decision.

If an exception applies, send it within a reasonable time.

What Should You Include in Your Complaint?

When you send a petition, make sure it is clear and complete. Include:

- Who is affected (the victim(s)).
- Your contact information.
- What happened: when, where, who was involved, and what took place.
- Which rights were violated.
- What you tried in your country's legal system.
- Any official responses you received.
- Copies of important documents (court decisions, previous complaints, etc.).
- Whether the case has been sent anywhere else (like the UN).

Important: Only send copies, not original documents. Keep a list of everything you send.

You don't need a lawyer, but getting legal help can make your complaint stronger.

What Happens After You Submit a Complaint?

The process includes several stages and may take several years to complete.

1.

You will receive a confirmation and reference number. The Commission will do a preliminary review and may:

- o Request more information,
- o Find the complaint inadmissible,
- o Open the case.

2.

If your case is open, you enter in the admissibility stage. In this stage:

- o The complaint is shared with the state.
- o Both parties exchange arguments and evidence.
- o The Commission decides if your complaint can move forward.

3.

If accepted, the Commission will check if your rights were violated (merits stage).

This involves:

- o Gathering evidence,
- o Possible hearings,
- o Attempting a friendly settlement between you and the State.

What Happens if the Commission Finds a Violation?

If the State is found responsible, the Commission will issue a report with non-binding recommendations, such as:

- Ending the rights violation,
- Investigating and punishing those responsible,
- Providing reparations (including symbolic or monetary),
- Reforming laws or practices.

If the State does not comply, the Commission may refer the case to the Inter-American Court, only if:

- The country has ratified the American Convention, and
- Accepted the Court's jurisdiction.

What Does the Inter-American Court Do?

The Court issues binding legal judgements for States under its jurisdiction.

However:

- Only the Commission or a State can bring a case to the Court. **Individuals cannot go directly.**
- If the Court finds a violation, the State is legally obligated to comply, though enforcement can be slow.

And if it is an emergency?

In urgent, serious situations with risk of irreparable harm, the Commission can request precautionary measures from the Court (e.g., ask the State to provide police protection, relocation, access to medical care).

These may be requested:

- Without a full complaint,
- While a complaint is pending.

You must explain:

- Why the danger is urgent and serious,
- What authorities you've informed,
- What kind of protection is needed.

What to Expect

- The process is long and can take 3–7 years or more.
- Free to submit, there is no cost.
- The process may put international pressure on your government.
- If the Commission grant recommendations, these are not legally binding.
- If criteria are met, the Court may issue a binding judgement.
- Your case may get public attention and support.

What Not to Expect

- A quick decision.
- Compensation or protection without a full legal process.
- Legal assistance from the Commission.
- Help with asylum, resettlement, or immigration procedures.
- Criminal punishment of perpetrators.
- Action against non-State actors (e.g., corporations).

Human Rights Committee

(CCPR)

What is the Human Rights Committee?

The Human Rights Committee (CCPR) is a group of independent experts that monitors how countries put into practice the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR).

If a country has agreed to follow both the ICCPR and its First Optional Protocol, people can send complaints to the Committee when their rights are violated. These rights include:

- The right to life
- Freedom from torture or cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment
- Freedom of expression and association
- The right to a fair trial
- Freedom of religion
- The right to take part in public affairs
- Protection of minority cultural, religious, and linguistic rights

Why is this important?

If your country has agreed to (ratified) the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) but is not respecting the rights it guarantees, you can bring the issue to the UN Human Rights Committee.

Cultural Rights Under the ICCPR: Article 27

Article 27 of the ICCPR protects the rights of persons belonging to ethnic, religious, or linguistic minorities:

“In those States in which ethnic, religious or linguistic minorities exist, persons belonging to such minorities shall not be denied the right, in community with the other members of their group, to enjoy their own culture, to profess and practise their own religion, or to use their own language.”

This provision has been interpreted to protect not only cultural expressions such as language and religion, but also economic and social activities that are integral to the culture of Indigenous, maroon or minority communities.

Cultural Rights Under the ICCPR: Article 27

Examples:

“The Committee finds that article 27, interpreted in the light of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples, enshrines the inalienable right of indigenous peoples to enjoy the territories and natural resources that they have traditionally used for their subsistence and cultural identity.”
(Perreira et al. vs Paraguay, para. 8.6)

“The Committee also recalls that, in the case of Indigenous Peoples, the enjoyment of culture may relate to a way of life which is closely associated with territory and the use of its resources, including such traditional activities as fishing or hunting. Thus, the protection of this right is directed towards ensuring the survival and continued development of cultural identity.”
(Billy and others v. Australia, para. 8.13)

Who Can File the Communication?

You can file an individual complaint (called a “communication”) if the following conditions are met:

1. The country you are complaining about must have:
 - o Ratified the ICCPR.
 - o Ratified the First Optional Protocol to the ICCPR (which allows the CCPR to hear individual complaints).
2. You are a victim (or representing a victim, with written consent) of an alleged violation by that State.

Important Caution

File Your Complaint With Support

It is strongly recommended that you file your complaint with the help of a qualified organisation, such as a human rights NGO, Indigenous or minority rights organisation, or a legal aid group with experience in international human rights mechanisms.

These procedures are complex, highly formal, and based on legal argumentation. Submitting an incomplete or poorly structured complaint can result in rejection without review. An experienced organization can help ensure that your case is admissible, clearly argued, and supported by appropriate evidence.

Against Whom is the Communication Made?

Your communication should be directed against your country's government, not against a person, company, or private group.

The government is responsible for making sure all the rights in the ICCPR are respected and protected.

Your complaint must relate to something the government has done, for example:

For example, passing laws that violate your rights (e.g. criminalising cultural practices).

Or something the government has failed to do:

For example, failing to regulate corporations that pollute Indigenous lands.

Even when a private actor (like a company) causes harm, the government can be held responsible if it failed to prevent or respond to the violation.

Think of your complaint as holding your State accountable for failing to uphold your rights under international law.

Before You File

You Must Exhaust Domestic Possibilities

Before you file a communication, you must first use all available legal channels in your own country, including appeals. Only after you have done so, and still have not received a remedy, can you file a communication.

Exceptions apply only when:

- National legal processes take too long.
- Legal options do not work or do not exist.
- You cannot safely or fairly use the legal system (for example, because of threats or discrimination).

Deadline for Submitting

You must send your complaint within five years after you have finished all possible national legal steps or from the moment it became clear that these steps would not work or were impossible to take.

How to Prepare Your Communication

Be clear and stick to the facts. Your communication should include:

- Which right was violated (say which ICCPR article, for example, Article 27).
- What happened (explain the facts — dates, people involved, what took place, and how it affected you).
- Evidence (attach anything that supports your case, like documents, court decisions, statements, photos, or news articles).
- What you want as a result (for example, compensation, a change in the law, official recognition, or a public apology).

No Double Filing

You cannot submit your case if:

- It is already being reviewed by another international or regional body (e.g. the Inter-American Court of Human Rights);
- You've already received a decision on the same matter from another UN body.

What to Expect and What Not to Expect

Filing a complaint with the UN Human Rights Committee can be useful, but you should have a realistic understanding of what the process can and cannot do.

Timeframe:

- Cases can take 2 to 5 years (or more) to be reviewed.
- The Committee works through written submissions; there are no in-person hearings.

Are the decisions binding?

The decisions are not legally binding like a court judgment. However, they carry strong moral and political weight, and many countries do respond positively by taking corrective measures.

What to Expect

- A thorough and independent review of your complaint.
- A public decision (called “views”) that may recommend reparations or legal changes.
- Your case to be used as precedent in other cases and advocacy work.
- International visibility and pressure that may help promote change at national level.

What Not to Expect

- A quick resolution.
- Financial compensation (unless your country later chooses to offer it).
- A reversal of national court decisions. The Committee does not act as an appeal court.
- Enforcement: The UN does not have a police force. It relies on state cooperation and international pressure.

Summary

If your cultural rights or other civil and political rights under the ICCPR have been violated, and your country has accepted the competence of the Human Rights Committee (by ratifying the First Optional Protocol), you may file a communication, once you've exhausted all available remedies in your national legal system.

Although the process is not fast and outcomes are not enforceable like court orders, it can be a powerful tool for visibility, international pressure, and gradual legal and policy change.

For more detailed guidance on preparing your communication, you should consult the official UN document titled: "Individual Complaints Procedures under the United Nations Human Rights Treaties and Guidance."

Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights

(CESCR)

UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights

If you believe your economic, social, or cultural rights have been violated, and your country has ratified certain international treaties, you may be able to bring your case to the United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR). This guide explains how to file such a communication, what to expect from the process, and the practical limitations you should be aware of.

What is the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights?

The United Nations Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (CESCR) is a group of independent experts that monitors how countries put into practice the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR).

If a country has agreed to follow the ICESCR, people can send complaints to the Committee when their rights are violated. These rights include:

- The right to education
- The right to health
- **The right to take part in cultural life**

Why is this important?

If your country has agreed to (ratified) the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) but is not respecting the rights it guarantees, you can bring the issue to the Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights.

Cultural Rights Under the ICESCR: Article 15

Article 15 of the ICESCR guarantees everyone's right to:

1. Take part in cultural life
2. Enjoy the benefits of scientific progress and its applications
3. Benefit from the protection of their scientific, literary, or artistic creations
4. Engage in scientific and cultural cooperation

Governments are obligated to take active steps to realise these rights and to respect the freedom required for cultural and scientific expression.

Who Can File the Communication?

You can file an individual complaint (called a “communication”) if the following conditions are met:

1. The country you are complaining about must have:
 - o Ratified the ICESCR.
 - o Ratified the Optional Protocol to the ICESCR (which allows the CESCO to hear individual complaints).
2. You are a victim (or representing a victim, with written consent) of an alleged violation by that State.

Important Caution:

It is strongly recommended that you file your complaint with the help of a qualified organisation, such as a human rights NGO, Indigenous or minority rights organisation, or a legal aid group with experience in international human rights mechanisms.

These procedures are complex, highly formal and based on legal argumentation. Submitting an incomplete or poorly structured complaint can result in rejection without review. An experienced organisation can help ensure that your case is admissible, clearly argued, and supported by appropriate evidence.

Against Whom is the Communication Made?

Your communication should be made against your country's government, not against a person, company, or private group.

The government is responsible for making sure all the rights in the ICESCR are respected and protected.

Your complaint must relate to something the government has done, for example:

For example, passing laws that violate your rights (e.g. criminalizing cultural practices)

Or something the government has failed to do:

For example, failing to regulate corporations that pollute Indigenous lands

Even when a private actor (like a company) causes harm, the government can be held responsible if it failed to prevent or respond to the violation.

Think of your complaint as holding your State accountable for failing to uphold your rights under international law.

Before You File

You Must Exhaust Domestic Possibilities

Before you file a communication, you must first use all available legal channels in your own country, including appeals. Only after you have done so, and still have not received a remedy, can you file a communication.

Exceptions apply only when:

- National legal processes take too long.
- Legal options do not work or do not exist.
- You cannot safely or fairly use the legal system (for example, because of threats or discrimination).

Deadline for Submitting

You must send your complaint within five years after you have finished all possible national legal steps or from the moment it became clear that these steps would not work or were impossible to take.

How to Prepare Your Communication

Be clear and stick to the facts. Your communication should include:

- Which right was violated (say which ICESCR article, for example, Article 15).
- What happened (explain the facts, dates, people involved, what took place, and how it affected you).
- Evidence (attach anything that supports your case, like documents, court decisions, statements, photos, or news articles).
- What you want as a result (for example, compensation, a change in the law, official recognition, or a public apology).

No Double Filing

You cannot submit your case if:

- It is already being reviewed by another international or regional body (e.g. the Inter-American Court of Human Rights);
- You've already received a decision on the same matter from another UN body.

What to Expect and What Not to Expect

Filing a complaint with the UN Committee on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights can be useful, but you should have a realistic understanding of what the process can and cannot do.

Timeframe:

- Cases can take 2 to 5 years (or more) to be reviewed.
- The Committee works through written submissions; there are no in-person hearings.

Are the decisions binding?

The decisions are not legally binding like a court judgment. However, they carry strong moral and political weight, and many countries do respond positively by taking corrective measures.

What to Expect

- A thorough and independent review of your complaint.
- A public decision (called “views”) that may recommend reparations or legal changes.
- Your case to be used as precedent in other cases and advocacy work.
- International visibility and pressure that may help promote change at national level.

What Not to Expect

- A quick resolution.
- Financial compensation (unless your country later chooses to offer it).
- A reversal of national court decisions. The Committee does not act as an appeal court.
- Enforcement: The UN does not have a police force. It relies on state cooperation and international pressure.

Summary

If your cultural rights or other economic and social rights under the ICESCR have been violated, and your country has accepted the competence of the Committee (by ratifying the Optional Protocol), you may file a communication, once you've exhausted all available remedies in your national legal system.

Although the process is not fast and outcomes are not enforceable like court orders, it can be a powerful tool for visibility, international pressure, and gradual legal and policy change.

For more detailed guidance on preparing your communication, you should consult the official UN document titled: "Individual Complaints Procedures under the United Nations Human Rights Treaties and Guidance."

International Labour Organisation

(ILO)

What is ILO?

The ILO, or International Labour Organisation, is the United Nations agency focused on work, workers' rights, and social justice.

The ILO has worked with Indigenous and Tribal Peoples for many years. In 1989, it adopted Convention 169, the only international treaty that focuses specifically on the rights of Indigenous and Tribal Peoples. This Convention protects important rights, including:

- **Consultation:** Communities have the right to be informed and consulted before decisions are made that affect them.
- **Land Rights:** People have the right to their land and resources.
- **Cultural identity:** Communities can preserve their ways of life.
- **Participation:** People have the right to take part in decisions that impact their lives.

Why is this important?

If your country has ratified ILO Convention 169 but is not respecting it, for example, by not consulting your community before approving a project on your land, you can bring the issue to the ILO's attention.

To do so, you must:

- Be part of an Indigenous or tribal people, as defined by Convention 169.
- Live in a country that has ratified the Convention.
- Coordinate with a trade union or organisation that is eligible to file a complaint.

You cannot file a complaint as an individual.

You will need to partner with a workers' organisation, or a cooperative that is formally recognised.

To increase your chances of success, work with legal experts.

Which community?

For this Convention, it is important to recall that:

Indigenous Peoples are defined as:

peoples in independent countries who are regarded as indigenous on account of their descent from the populations which inhabited the country, or a geographical region to which the country belongs, at the time of conquest or colonisation or the establishment of present state boundaries and who, irrespective of their legal status, retain some or all of their own social, economic, cultural and political institutions. (Article 1(b)).

Tribal Peoples are defined as:

tribal peoples in independent countries whose social, cultural and economic conditions distinguish them from other sections of the national community, and whose status is regulated wholly or partially by their own customs or traditions or by special laws or regulations. (Article 1(a)).

What to Expect

- The ILO may publicly recognise that a violation occurred.
- The ILO may recommend actions the government should take, such as changing a law, improving consultation procedures, or compensating affected communities.
- The process can lead to increased national and international attention, which may pressure governments to act.
- The ILO can monitor the government's follow-up steps over time.

What Not to Expect

- The ILO cannot force a government to act, its decisions and recommendations are not legally binding.
- The ILO cannot provide compensation directly to victims.
- The process can take months or even years to be completed.
- There is no guarantee of a specific outcome.

Still, the process may be an important step in pushing your government to meet its responsibilities and in raising awareness about the violation of your rights.

There Are Two Main Ways to File a Complaint

**Representation under
Article 24 of the ILO
Constitution**

**Complaint under
Article 26 of the ILO
Constitution**

What Is a Representation?

This is the most accessible option for communities and organisations.

A Representation is a formal written complaint stating that a country is not following the rules of a ratified ILO Convention, in this case, Convention 169.

Who Can File?

Only workers' organisations or employers' organisations can submit a representation. This includes:

- Trade unions;
- Indigenous or Tribal peoples' organizations (if organized as workers' associations);
- Cooperatives (e.g., of fishers, farmers, artisans);
- Farmers' or campesino unions;
- National or international workers' associations.

You must be a recognized organization: individuals cannot file on their own.

The organization does not have to be directly affected by the issue.

Against Whom is the Complaint Made?

Complaints under ILO Convention No. 169 are made against a State (government), not against a company, individual, or private organisation.

ILO Convention No. 169 places clear responsibilities on governments to respect, protect, and fulfil the rights of Indigenous and Tribal Peoples. This includes ensuring participation, protecting lands and resources, and respecting cultural and social integrity.

Your complaint must concern actions or omissions by the government that violate its obligations under Convention 169. This may include:

- Failing to consult Indigenous or Tribal peoples before adopting laws or projects affecting them;
- Not recognizing or protecting traditional land rights;
- Authorizing extractive or infrastructure projects on Indigenous or Tribal lands without free, prior, and informed consent;
- Undermining Indigenous or Tribal institutions or cultures;
- Neglecting to provide services such as education, health care, and justice in culturally appropriate ways.

Against Whom is the Complaint Made?

Even if a private company or third party caused harm, the government can be held responsible if it failed to regulate or prevent such harm, or did not provide access to justice or remedies.

In these complaints, the focus is on whether the State has respected its legal duties under Convention 169, which it accepted by ratifying the Convention.

What to Include in the Representation?

1. Written format in a common language (English, French or Spanish).
2. Your organisation's identity, purpose, and legal status.
3. The country involved that must have ratified Convention.
4. A clear reference to Article 24 of the ILO Constitution.
5. The name of the Convention.
6. A detailed explanation of the violation, with supporting evidence (documents, testimonies, photos, reports, media articles).

What Happens After Submission?

1. The ILO checks the formal requirements: Is your organisation eligible? Is the complaint valid?
2. If accepted, a tripartite committee (representing governments, workers, and employers) is formed to examine the issue.
3. The government is asked to respond.
4. The committee may ask for more information or conduct a country visit.
5. The committee writes a report with its conclusions and recommendations.
6. The ILO's Governing Body makes a final decision on the case.
7. The findings are usually published and the government is asked to take corrective steps.

What Is a Complaint?

This is a more formal and rare process.

Who Can File?

- Another ILO member country.
- A delegate to the International Labour Conference.
- The ILO Governing Body itself.

Local organisations and communities cannot file this kind of complaint directly.

What Happens in an Article 26 Complaint?

1. A Commission of Inquiry (3 independent experts) investigates the case.
2. They gather written and oral information, and may conduct hearings or site visits.
3. A detailed report is published with findings and recommendations.
4. If the country does not follow the recommendations, the ILO can take further steps, including referring the case to the International Court of Justice.

This process is rare and usually used in cases of serious and repeated violations.

Summary

If your community wants to raise concerns about a violation of Convention 169, the most accessible route is through an Article 24 Representation, in partnership with an eligible organisation.

- Document everything clearly.
- Partner with experienced organisations or legal experts.
- Understand the process may be long and outcomes uncertain, but it is still a valuable tool to make your voice heard and hold states accountable.

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